

The Effect of Emotional Exhaustion and Emotional Labor on Cargo Employees' Turnover Intentions and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study is to examine the effect of the emotional labor of cargo company employees on emotional exhaustion, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. Cargo company employees have a labor-intensive job design. Therefore, they may encounter many physical and mental difficulties in their jobs. The study also evaluates whether employees' expressions of their emotions during the work process are a precursor to explaining turnover intention, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion. A quantitative research method is used in the study. The survey technique is used as the data collection method. Data was collected from a total of 247 cargo employees in the study. Data were analyzed in the Smart PLS statistical program. Accordingly, frequency, variety, and surface acting have positive effects, and deep acting has negative effects on emotional labor. On the other hand, intensity does not affect emotional labor. In addition, emotional labor has a negative effect on job satisfaction, but it does not affect turnover intention. Finally, job satisfaction does not affect turnover intention.

Keywords: Cargo workers, emotional labor, job satisfaction, turnover intention, emotional exhaustion

JEL Classification: M12, J28, J63, M54, C83

1. Introduction

The growth of the service sector has increased the importance of employees' emotional labor and has attracted increasing attention in various fields, including organizational behavior and organizational psychology (Grandey & Gabriel, 2015). In addition to the stress caused by the intense pace of work life and urbanization, the intensity and administrative situations experienced in the workplace affect the

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service performance of employees. Especially for employees working in the labor-intensive service sector, intensity and stress also affect emotional changes in individuals, such as burnout. In this context, factors such as intensity and stress negatively affect the job satisfaction of employees, and this situation leads to results such as leaving the job. The most important factor that keeps organizations alive and provides them with a competitive advantage is undoubtedly their employees. Therefore, leaving the job is considered one of the primary problems for organizations. The reasons for leaving the job in organizations, the negative factors affecting the level of job satisfaction, and the intention to leave the job as a result of these have been addressed, especially in studies on organizational behavior and human resources.

The concept of emotional labor, which includes the ability to manage and express emotions, engage in social interaction, and skills of individuals (Boyd, 2002; Pagne, 2006), is a concept that includes the elements of frequency, intensity, variety, surface acting, and deep acting (Morris and Feldman, 1996). Each of these dimensions is defined as the labor elements that a person exerts for the job he/she has (Chaves-Montero et al., 2025). Emotional exhaustion is a concept related to the person's state of mind and is the depletion of the person's internal resources and motivation due to consequences such as failure and wear and tear (Wicaksana & Wijayanti, 2025). The job satisfaction level of individuals experiencing emotional exhaustion will decrease. Job satisfaction is the positive feelings a person feels towards the job he/she does in different dimensions such as psychological, physiological, environmental, and economic (Comparcini et al., 2025). Job satisfaction is seen as one of the most important elements in the continuity and loyalty of individuals to work. Many negative emotions may arise in individuals who are not satisfied with their jobs, and it can be said that the highest level of these emotions is the intention to quit. Intention refers to the behaviors that an individual foresees and plans for the future (Swan, 1981). Intention to quit is defined as a conscious decision made by employees with the desire to leave their job ties with the organization they work for (Tett & Meyer, 1993).

This study aims to determine the effects of emotional exhaustion and emotional labor on the intention to quit and job satisfaction levels of cargo employees. In particular, no research has been found in Turkey that examines the effects of emotional expressions on the job quitting and job satisfaction of employees working in cargo companies. This situation can be shown as an example of the originality of the study.

2. Literature Review

Trade Many studies conducted in the service and industry sectors have found that the emotional labor required by organizational norms can negatively affect individual well-being (Hülshager & Schewe, 2011). Grandey (2000) stated that emotional labor can negatively affect employees' job satisfaction and that job satisfaction has strong effects on attendance, turnover, sabotage, job performance, and employees' mental and physical health (Miao et al., 2017). Emotional labor also

negatively affects employees by affecting the performance of the organization. Among several factors leading to intention to leave, burnout plays an important role (Kilo & Hassmén, 2016), and surface acting has been found to contribute to burnout, job dissatisfaction, and intention to leave (Lee & Chelladurai, 2018). The departure of qualified employees will result in additional costs in recruiting, hiring, and training new employees. It will also have negative effects on the service quality of the organization. Therefore, a higher turnover rate will negatively affect the business performance of organizations. In turn, it will negatively affect the job stability of the remaining employees. Therefore, it is important to address the emotional labor problems of employees to improve organizational performance, increase employee motivation, and increase employee job satisfaction. Since frontline employees, especially in the service sector, are the “barometer of the job” (Dagger et al., 2013), organizations try to provide various supports to their employees at service contact points (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kim et al., 2017). Social support is one of the supports that can be provided to employees, as it has long been defined as a resource that enables people to cope with stress (Wright and Hobfoll, 2002). Social support is roughly defined as “the existence and quality of helpful relationships” (Leavy, 1983) and can be provided by coworkers, supervisors, and the organization. Recently, since emotions are common among customers in service encounters (Gabriel et al., 2016), many studies have emphasized the importance of emotional intelligence, which refers to the ability of employees to control their emotions and empathize with customers. On this subject, Mayer stated that “the ability to perceive emotions, integrate emotions to facilitate thinking, and understand and manage emotions to promote personal growth are crucial for professional success and mental health and well-being” (Wang et al., 2016). Hochschild (1979; 1983) described two types of emotional labor based on the performance approach to the dimensions of emotional labor. The first of these is surface acting, which refers to the employee recreating emotions that are not truly felt by changing their external appearance, such as facial expressions, movements, or tone of voice, while displaying the necessary emotions. The second is deep acting, which can be defined as behaviors that the agent exhibits when their emotions do not fit the situation, using their preparations or past experiences to later express appropriate emotions. Although Ashforth and Mael (1989) added another dimension, Genuine Emotion, to Hochschild's work and proposed three main dimensions, it is generally accepted that emotional labor is dimensionalized in two ways, Surface Acting and Deep Acting (Hochschild, 1983).

Especially in the service sector, communication is considered to be one of the most important factors between customers and employees. Communication can be defined as an important means of interaction that controls and connects the relationships of a person with others as a member of society (Gabbott et al., 2011). In service encounters, nonverbal and verbal expressions are important factors affecting customer satisfaction and job performance (Gayathridevi, 2013). Since communication between employees and customers in service encounters can be a differentiating factor that distinguishes a company from its competitors, it is important to manage verbal and nonverbal communication carried out by employees to increase the quality of interaction between employees and customers. One of the most negative situations encountered in labor-intensive businesses is

seen as emotional exhaustion. Emotional exhaustion refers to feelings of exhaustion due to work and is conceptually referred to as a chronic response to work stress situations associated with high levels of human contact (Maslach, 1982). In other words, emotional exhaustion can be defined as physical and emotional exhaustion symptoms, including a negative self-concept, a negative attitude towards work, and loss of interest or emotion towards the customer (Maslach, 1982). At the same time, emotional exhaustion is defined as the negative psychological experience of a person responsible for a job with high interpersonal contact experiences being exposed to long-term stress (Maslach and Schaufeli, 1993). Job satisfaction is a personal reaction and can be defined as an emotional response to a task or job (Bhuiyan and Mengue, 2002). Job satisfaction is determined not only by the difference between the expectations recognized by employees and experience, but also by the relationship between the organizational environment and personal characteristics, such as the relationship between the manager and the employee (Gayathridevi, 2013). Employees with low job satisfaction will tend to leave the job, which will increase the employee turnover rate in the organization. An increase in employee turnover will also reduce the desire of other employees to stay in the company, and the departure of qualified employees will cause additional costs in recruiting, hiring, and training new employees (Price, 2001). At the same time, a high employee turnover rate will have negative effects on the service quality of the organization and will negatively affect the Model

3. Hypothesis Development

Frequency is an expression related to how long and at what intervals a behavior is performed. Continuous display of behavior creates a feeling of cooling towards that behavior in the person after a certain period (Moreno-Martinez & Sanchez-Martinez, 2025). Continuous display of behavior will create a feeling of exhaustion and boredom towards that behavior and cause a decrease in performance in the person when the behavior is displayed (Peng et al., 2025). Intensity can be expressed as the degree or level of display of a behavior. Similar to frequency, an intense display of behavior and excessive emotion causes the person to develop a feeling of cooling towards the relevant behavior after a certain period. Considering the relationship between frequency and intensity and emotional exhaustion in the literature, the relevant hypotheses of the study are stated below:

H1. Frequency positively affects emotional exhaustion.

H2. Intensity positively affects emotional exhaustion.

The behaviors that people constantly exhibit become compatible with their personality structures after a certain period, and these behaviors turn into deep playfulness (Lim & Lee, 2025). However, the necessity to constantly behave in different ways can tire the person and cause the person to become disenchanted

with that behavior and work (Sharma et al., 2025). Considering the relationships between diversity and emotional exhaustion in literature, the relevant hypotheses of the study are stated below:

H3. Variety positively affects emotional exhaustion.

Surface acting behavior has an effect that increases the level of burnout in employees (Süzer, 2025). Since surface acting is behavior that employees do not feel but exhibit out of necessity, this situation causes a feeling of boredom to develop in people over time (Grandey, 2000). When people display emotions that they do not feel, it will create a psychological burden on them, and this burden will cause them to exhibit negative attitudes towards their jobs over time (Horchschild, 1983). Considering the relationships between surface acting and emotional burnout in the literature, the relevant hypotheses of the study are stated below:

H4. Surface acting positively affects emotional exhaustion.

Deep acting refers to people exhibiting a behavior because it comes from within them. In this case, natural behaviors are exhibited, and people feel much more comfortable because there is no sense of obligation (Gaan, 2012). It can be said that people who can display their own emotions are happier in the work environment, and their levels of commitment and satisfaction will increase (Awan, 2025). Considering the relationship between deep acting and emotional exhaustion in the literature, the relevant hypotheses of the study are stated below:

H5. Deep acting negatively affects emotional exhaustion.

Emotional exhaustion is a concept related to the individual's mood and can be defined as the depletion of one's internal resources as a result of failure and wear and tear (Wicaksana & Wijayanti, 2025). It is a chronic reaction to stressful work situations (Mikolajezak et al., 2007) and causes people to distance themselves from their jobs, become estranged, and adopt negative emotions (Van Strydonck et al., 2025). Job satisfaction can be defined as people's positive and enjoyable feelings towards their job (Maeran et al., 2013). In this direction, it has been determined in many studies that individuals who feel a sense of burnout will adopt negative emotions towards their jobs, and their satisfaction levels will decrease (Wicaksana & Wijayanti, 2025; Strydonck, 2025). Considering the relationships between emotional burnout and job satisfaction in the literature, the relevant hypotheses of the study are stated below:

H6. Emotional exhaustion negatively affects job satisfaction.

Emotional exhaustion, which occurs for many different reasons such as intense working conditions, stress, and decreased productivity (Chaves-Montero et al., 2025), can cause many different negative behaviors such as absenteeism

and non-compliance with working hours (Bruyneel et al., 2025). The most radical of these reasons is the intention to leave the job. The intention to leave the job can be defined as a consciously planned decision-making process before people decide to resign (Ivana et al., 2025). Individuals whose satisfaction level decreases with emotional exhaustion will decrease their continuation in that job (Ju & Hyun, 2025; Terry et al., 2025). Considering the relationship between emotional exhaustion and intention to leave the job in literature, the relevant hypothesis of the study is stated below:

H7. Emotional exhaustion positively affects intention to leave.

Job satisfaction, defined as a person's feeling of psychological, physiological, and environmental happiness towards their job (Comparcini et al., 2025), enables people to be happy in their jobs and to develop a sense of belonging and loyalty to that job (Brady et al., 2025). Therefore, it is expected that people who are satisfied with their jobs do not intend to leave their jobs (Etti et al., 2025). As the level of satisfaction with the job increases, job continuity and commitment will increase at the same rate (Kauppila, 2025). In this direction, considering the relationship between job satisfaction and intention to leave in the literature, the relevant hypothesis of the study is stated below:

H8. Job satisfaction negatively affects intention to leave.

Figure 1. Research Model exports.

4. Data and Methodology

This study was conducted with individuals who work in any cargo company and are over the age of 18. The universe of study was formed by these individuals. However, since it was not possible to reach all employees, sampling was preferred. Data was collected using the convenience sampling method. Since the size of the universe was unknown, Roscoe's (1975) view that a sample size of 30-500 would be sufficient was taken into account in determining the sample size. Accordingly, data was collected from 247 participants face-to-face. Before data collection, the survey form used in the study was pilot tested on a group of 30 people. Based on the data obtained, the reliability of the scales was tested, and all scale statements yielded reliable results. Before filling out the survey form, the participants were asked whether they volunteered, and the study continued with those who volunteered.

Data Collection and Analysis Method

A questionnaire form was used to collect data in the study. Categorical data related to the demographic characteristics of the participants were used in the questionnaire form. For this purpose, the gender and age distribution of the participants were asked. When the obtained results were examined, 61.9% of the participants were male and 38.1% were female. 50.2% of the participants were 25-34, 22.3% were 35-44, 20.2% were 18-24, and 7.3% were 45 and above. The sub-sub-dimension was used to measure the emotional labor of the participants in the study. Three items were used to measure frequency, two statements were used to measure intensity, three items were used to measure variety, and the included items were used to measure surface acting and deep acting (Brotheridge & Lee, 2002). Four items were used to measure job satisfaction (Nadiri & Tanova, 2010), nine items were used to measure emotional exhaustion (Anđelković et al., 2017), and three items were used to measure turnover intention (Nadiri & Tanova, 2010). All items were asked of the participants on a five-point Likert-type scale with ends of never or always.

The Smart PLS statistical program was used to analyze the data. After the scale items were subjected to validity and reliability analysis, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the hypotheses. The reason for using the Smart PLS statistical program is that it does not require distribution normality and works on small data sets (Hair et al., 2019). Common method bias was examined by performing Harman's single-factor analysis, and it was found that when all factors were collected in a single-factor structure, they did not explain most of the covariance, and it was below the conservative threshold of 50% (Doty & Glick, 1998; Podsakoff & Organ, 1986).

Measurement model assessment

Confirmatory factor analysis was applied to test the construct validity of the scales used in the study, and the factor loadings of all scale expressions were over 0.50 (Kaiser, 1974). Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (rho_c and rho_a) were calculated to assess the internal consistency of the scales. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of all scales was over 0.70. The reliability score of turnover intention was over 0.60. Although this result was below 0.70, it was accepted because the rho_c value was over 0.60 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). The rho_a values of the scales were also over 0.70 (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015). The rho_c values of the other scales were also over the 0.70 threshold. For concurrent validity, average variance extracted (AVE) was calculated, and AVE values of all scales were above 0.50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). All these results are shown in detail in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables Reliability and Validity Scores

Variables	λ	α	rho_a	rho_c	AVE
Emotional Labor					
<i>Frequency</i>					
1 Fr1	0,934	0,883	0,884	0,928	0,812
2 Fr2	0,869				
3 Fr3	0,899				
<i>Intensity</i>					
1 Int1	0,902	0,792	0,795	0,906	0,827
6 Int2	0,917				
<i>Variety</i>					
1 Vr1	0,910	0,869	0,873	0,919	0,792
2 Vr2	0,885				
4 Vr3	0,874				
<i>Surface acting (SA)</i>					
1 SA1	0,921	0,890	0,903	0,931	0,818
2 SA2	0,915				
4 SA3	0,877				
<i>Deep acting (DA)</i>					
1 DA1	0,907	0,883	0,883	0,928	0,811
2 DA2	0,905				
5 DA3	0,890				
Emotional exhaustion (EE)					
1 EE1	0,843	0,957	0,958	0,963	0,743
2 EE2	0,863				
3 EE3	0,846				
4 EE4	0,852				
5 EE5	0,866				
6 EE6	0,875				
7 EE7	0,877				
8 EE8	0,883				
9 EE9	0,853				
Job satisfaction (JB)					
1 JB1	0,902	0,909	0,918	0,936	0,784
2 JB2	0,911				
3 JB3	0,867				
4 JB4	0,861				
**Turnover intention (TI)					
1 TI1	0,751	0,627	0,626	0,801	0,573
2 TI2	0,784				
3 TI3	0,735				

λ =Outer loadings, α =Cronbach Alpha, rho_a and rho_c=Composite reliability, AVE=Average variance extracted

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was examined to determine the discriminant validity of the scales. The results obtained are shown in Table 2. When the analysis was examined, the AVE square root values were higher than the correlation loads of all scales with others (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). In this context, the scales provided discriminant validity

Table 2. Fornell Larcker Criterion

No	Construct	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Deep acting	0,900							
2	Emotional exhaustion	-0,663	0,862						
3	Frequency	-0,683	0,695	0,901					
4	Intensity	-0,620	0,603	0,655	0,910				
5	Job satisfaction	0,614	-0,635	-0,605	-0,632	0,886			
6	Surface acting	-0,651	0,674	0,614	0,588	-0,611	0,905		
7	Turnover intention	-0,163	0,143	0,172	0,235	-0,144	0,082	0,757	
8	Variety	-0,639	0,634	0,640	0,611	-0,572	0,623	0,237	0,890

Note. Numbers in bold represent the square root of AVE

Hypothesis Testing

Within the scope of the research purpose, hypotheses were tested in a structural equation model. Accordingly, frequency and variety have a significant effect on emotional exhaustion. So, H1 and H3 were supported. However, intensity does not affect emotional exhaustion. Hence, H2 was not supported. Also, surface acting has a positive effect on emotional exhaustion, and deep acting has a negative effect on emotional exhaustion. Therefore, H4 and H5 were supported. While emotional exhaustion has a negative effect on job satisfaction, it does not affect turnover intention. So, while H6 was supported, H7 was not supported. Lastly, job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention. Hence, H8 was supported. The results obtained are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Structural Equation Model Results

Hypotheses	β	\bar{x}	SD	t-statistics	p-value	Result
H ₁ Fr -> EE	0,285	0,284	0,061	4,647	0,000***	Supported
H ₂ Int -> EE	0,077	0,075	0,058	1,327	0,184	Not supported
H ₃ Var -> EE	0,137	0,139	0,055	2,509	0,012**	Supported
H ₄ SA -> EE	0,262	0,261	0,056	4,715	0,000***	Supported
H ₅ DA -> EE	-0,162	-0,164	0,069	2,362	0,018**	Supported
H ₆ EE -> JS	-0,636	-0,635	0,047	13,633	0,000***	Supported
H ₇ EE -> TI	0,086	0,089	0,099	0,875	0,382	Not supported
H ₈ JS -> TI	-0,089	-0,093	0,104	0,854	0,393	Not supported

p=<0.001***, p=<0.05**

5. Results

This research examined the effects of emotional labor components of individuals working in the cargo sector on emotional exhaustion and the effect of emotional exhaustion on job satisfaction and intention to leave. The evaluation was tested with SEM based on the research model. When the research results were examined, it was determined that frequency positively and significantly affected emotional exhaustion. The frequency of emotional labor increases emotional exhaustion. In other words, it is seen that employees' frequent regulation of their emotions causes it to become a chronic source of stress and triggers emotional exhaustion. This result is parallel to the findings of researchers such as Brotheridge and Grandey (2002) and Cheung and Tang (2010) that the frequency of emotional labor can increase psychological exhaustion. Secondly, the effect of intensity on emotional exhaustion was investigated in the research, and it was concluded that intensity did not have a significant effect on emotional exhaustion. In other words, it was found that intensive emotional labor did not directly lead to burnout in cargo employees. The reason for this can be shown as the intensity of emotions varies from individual to individual. The reason for such a result may be that some cargo workers are more resistant to situations that require high emotional effort. A similar situation emerges when looking at the studies of Glomb and Tews (2004). In other words, it is seen that some types of intensity may be related to emotional resilience.

Thirdly, it was determined in the study that diversity has a positive and significant effect on emotional exhaustion. In broader terms, the fact that cargo workers display different emotional expressions increases their emotional exhaustion. The fact that employees have to take on different emotional roles means that they exhaust their mental resources and their self-integrity is challenged (Rafaeli & Sutton, 1987; Hülshager & Schewe, 2011). This situation is likely to be seen in service sector employees who are in constant interaction with customers. Cargo workers are also in constant interaction with customers. Fourthly, it was determined in the study that surface acting has a positive and significant effect on emotional exhaustion. Cargo workers expressing emotions they do not feel causes them to experience emotional exhaustion. This result supports the psychological damage theory of surface acting written by Hochschild (1983) regarding emotional labor. In addition, as Grandey (2003) stated, surface acting creates emotional dissonance in individuals. This causes the individual to experience conflicts regarding their true self.

Another result that emerged in the study is that deep acting negatively and significantly affects emotional exhaustion. In other words, it is observed that emotional exhaustion decreases in cases where cargo employees truly feel and exhibit behaviors. This situation shows that deep acting enables the person to act more in harmony with their true self. Naturally, it is observed that there is no emotional dissonance in the employee, and emotional exhaustion does not occur (Brotheridge & Lee, 2002; Diefendorff et al., 2005). As a result, it is observed that deep acting increases the psychological resilience of the employees.

In the study, it was determined that emotional exhaustion negatively and significantly affects job satisfaction. In other words, the fact that cargo employees do not experience emotional exhaustion ensures that they are satisfied with their jobs. It is seen that the burnout theory developed by Maslach and Jackson (1981) is also important for employees, with this result. In addition, this result is parallel to the results obtained by Kalliath and Morris (2002).

Emotional exhaustion does not have a significant effect on intention to leave. This result is a surprising result regarding this study conducted on cargo workers. However, it is understood from this that there are reasons other than emotional exhaustion that are effective in cargo workers' decisions to leave their jobs. This reason may be economic conditions, job security, or alternative employment opportunities (Taris et al., 2001). In addition, the possibility of cargo workers doing this job, considering economic conditions, may have also led to this result. Finally, the effect of job satisfaction on intention to leave the job was evaluated in the study. As a result, it was found that job satisfaction did not affect intention to leave the job. Similar studies in literature have concluded that job satisfaction triggers intention to leave the job (Locke, 1976). However, when recent studies are examined, it is seen that this situation may vary according to contextual and cultural factors (Chen et al., 2011). Considering the difficult economic conditions in Turkey, the probability of such a result is high.

Practical Implications

The findings obtained in this study showed that the intense emotional labor demand in the cargo service sector can lead to serious emotional burnout in employees. It is observed that the psychological resilience of employees decreases, especially in cases of superficial acting and frequency. It is important to review human resources policies in cargo services and to act in an employee-focused manner. Institutionally, it is necessary to value employee emotions and to create the necessary training and sincere business relationships for the formation of deep acting. For this purpose, strategies should be developed to establish authentic customer relationships, especially from an organizational perspective (Grandey, 2003). On the other hand, an infrastructure should be established where employees can convey their negativities, and an organizational climate should be developed where they can express their emotions comfortably instead of suppressing them. As a support mechanism, psychological counseling services, pieces of training such as emotional awareness, and therapy opportunities can be applied (Hülshager & Schewe, 2011).

When the study results are examined, it has been determined that deep acting has a reducing effect on emotional exhaustion in cargo employees. Therefore, plans can be made to develop deep acting skills in employees as a strategic action to reduce emotional exhaustion. In other words, awareness training can be given to use their emotional intelligence and cope with their emotions (Diefendorff et al., 2005). On the other hand, the necessity of cargo employees to display various emotional expressions also increases burnout. For

this, certain standards can be set regarding the customer interaction process, and employees can be minimally affected by this situation. Naturally, in this way, quality inter-employee relations can be developed in the workplace, and possible problems between customers and employees will be prevented.

Theoretical Implications

The findings obtained in this study support Hochschild's (1983) emotional labor theory. The situation in which surface acting increases emotional exhaustion is explained in this study specifically for cargo workers. This situation is also a reference to the relevant theory. It is confirmed that people's expression of their emotions is closely related to their true selves. In addition, the fact that deep acting reduces emotional exhaustion shows that emotional labor is not a structurally homogeneous concept and that different strategies reveal different psychological interests (Grandey, 2000). While these results emphasize that strategic distinctions should be made in the emotional labor literature, they show that emotional labor is not only a behavioral process but also a cognitive and affective process (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1993).

The research results confirm the relationship between emotional exhaustion and job satisfaction. This result is consistent with Maslach and Jackson's (1981) burnout model. However, it was found in this study that leaving the job is not only related to work-related psychological processes but can also be caused by external factors. The fact that the study was conducted in Turkey and was particularly focused on cargo workers may also be the reason for these results. Therefore, when the relationship is established with social exchange theory (Blau, 1964) and organizational commitment theories (Meyer & Allen, 1991), the necessity of examining the emotional labor process and emotional burnout in more depth in the service sector emerges based on the results. In summary, this study provides a multidimensional framework to understand how emotional labor transforms into organizational outcomes through burnout in cargo service sector employees and adds contextual depth to the emotional labor literature.

Limitations and Future Research

This study has several limitations. The study was designed only for cargo service workers. Therefore, its generalizability to the entire service sector is limited. Since the data collection process was based on a cross-sectional design, causal relationships between variables could not be tested directly. Longitudinal studies can be recommended to understand the changes in psychological processes, such as emotional labor and burnout, over time. On the other hand, the study was conducted only based on a self-report survey. In future studies, different measurements and evaluations can be made using observation, diary methods, or neurophysiological tools. In addition, evaluations can be made on mediating variables that address economic or other issues to understand the intention to leave the job more clearly.

References

- Anđelković, A., Đorđević, B., & Arsić, M. (2017). Emotional exhaustion in the workplace—the role of human resource management. *Ekonomika*, 63(1), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.5937/ekonomika1701045A>
- Ashforth, B. E., & Humphrey, R. H. (1993). Emotional labor in service roles: The influence of identity. *Academy of Management Review*, 18(1), 88–115.
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. (1989). Social identity theory and organization. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(1), 20-39.
- Awan, N. J. (2025). Navigating affective commitment and turnover intention: the mediating role of job satisfaction in charismatic leadership effects within Pakistan's pharmaceutical industry. *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*, 3(2), 83-110.
- Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (1988). On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 16(1), 74–94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02723327>
- Bhuian, S. N., & Mengue, B. (2002). An extension and evaluation of job characteristics, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction in an expatriate, guest worker, sales setting. *J. Pers. Selling Sales Manag.* 22, 1–11.
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. Wiley.
- Brotheridge, C. M., & Grandey, A. A. (2002). Emotional labor and burnout: Comparing two perspectives of “people work.” *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 60(1), 17–39. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1815>
- Boyd, R. L. (2002). Urban unemployment, the rural labor market, and southern blacks in farm labor during the Great Depression: a research note. *The Social Science Journal*, 39(2), 295-299.
- Brady, N., O'Connell, S., Gilligan, D., Madden, C., Gannon, L., Howson, V., ... & Drennan, J. (2025). Planned Changes to Nurse Leadership, Staffing, and Skill Mix: Impact on the Working Environment, Job Satisfaction, and Intention to Leave. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*.
- Bruyneel, A., Dello, S., Dauvergne, J. E., Kohnen, D., & Sermeus, W. (2025). Prevalence and risk factors for burnout, missed nursing care, and intention to leave the job among intensive care unit and general ward nurses: A cross-sectional study across six European countries in the COVID-19 era. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing*, 86, 103885.
- Chaves-Montero, A., Blanco-Miguel, P., & Ríos-Vizcaíno, B. (2025, March). Analysis of the predictors and consequential factors of emotional exhaustion among social workers: A systematic review. *Healthcare*, 13(5), Article 552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare13050552>
- Cheung, F. Y., & Tang, C. S. (2010). The influence of emotional labor on work-family interference: A study of Chinese secondary school teachers. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(4), 813–833.
- Comparcini, D., Simonetti, V., Totaro, M., Apicella, A., Galli, F., Toccaceli, A., ... & Tomietto, M. (2025). Impact of traumatic stress on nurses' work ability, job satisfaction, turnover, and intention to leave: A cross-sectional study.

- Journal of Nursing Management, 33(1), 18–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13908>
- Dagger, T. S., Danaher, P. J., Sweeney, J. C., & McColl-Kennedy, J. R. (2013). Selective halo effects arising from improving the interpersonal skills of frontline employees. *Journal of Service Research*, 16(4), 488-502.
- Diefendorff, J. M., Croyle, M. H., & Gosserand, R. H. (2005). The dimensionality and antecedents of emotional labor strategies. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66(2), 339–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2004.02.001>
- Dijkstra, T. K., & Henseler, J. (2015). Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Quarterly*, 39(2), 297–316.
<https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2015/39.2.02>
- Doty, D. H., & Glick, W. H. (1998). Common methods bias: Does common methods variance really bias results? *Organizational Research Methods*, 1(4), 374–406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442819814002>
- Eisenberger, R., Stinglhamber, F., Vandenberghe, C., Sucharski, I. L., & Rhoades, L. (2002). Perceived supervisor support: contributions to perceived organizational support and employee retention. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(3), 565.
- Etti, N., Irit, B., & Michal, I. (2025). Caring for Patients with Infectious Diseases: Nurses' Risk Perception, Moral Distress, Professional Ethos, and Emotional Labor: A Mixed Methods Study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378101800104>
- Gaan, N. (2012). Impact of emotional labor on teaching effectiveness: A study of higher education in India. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 47(4), 673-684.
- Gabbott, M., Tsarenko, Y., & Mok, W. H. (2011). Emotional intelligence as a moderator of coping strategies and service outcomes in circumstances of service failure. *Journal of Service Research*, 14(2), 234-248.
- Gabriel, A. S., Cheshin, A., Moran, C. M., & Van Kleef, G. A. (2016). Enhancing emotional performance and customer service through human resources practices: A systems perspective. *Human Resource Management Review*, 26(1), 14-24.
- Gayathridevi, K. S. (2013). A study on nonverbal communication of salespersons and their service behavior towards customers in a sales encounter. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Management*, 8(4), 83.
- Grandey, A. A. (2000). Emotion regulation in the workplace: A new way to conceptualize emotional labor. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 5(1), 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.5.1.95>
- Grandey, A. A. (2003). When “the show must go on”: Surface acting and deep acting as determinants of emotional exhaustion and peer-rated service delivery. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46(1), 86–96.
- Grandey, A. A., & Gabriel, A. S. (2015). Emotional labor at a crossroads: Where do we go from here? *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and*

- Organizational Behavior, 2(1), 323–349. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032414-111400>
- Glomb, T. M., & Tews, M. J. (2004). Emotional labor: A conceptualization and scale development. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 64(1), 1–23.
- Hochschild, A. R. (1983). *The managed heart: Commercialization of human feeling*. University of California Press.
- Hochschild, A. R. (1979). Emotion work, feeling rules, and social structure. *American Journal of Sociology*, 85(3), 551-575.
- Hülshager, U. R., & Schewe, A. F. (2011). On the costs and benefits of emotional labor: a meta-analysis of three decades of research. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 16(3), 361-389.
- Ivana, P. R., Marumpe, D. P., Daud, I., & Yakin, I. (2025). Impact of psychological contract breach and ethical leadership on turnover intention: Emotional exhaustion as mediator. *Journal of Management Science (JMAS)*, 8(1), 243-253.
- Ju, H., & Hyun, S. S. (2025). Impact of the burnout symptoms of flight attendants on absenteeism and turnover intention: the moderating role of emotional intelligence. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 27(1), e70007.
- Kaiser, H. F. (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika*, 39(1), 31-36.
- Kalliath, T., & Morris, R. (2002). Job satisfaction among nurses: A predictor of burnout levels. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 32(12), 648–654.
- Kauppara, O. P. (2025). Revisiting the relationships between leadership and job satisfaction. *European Management Review*, 22(1), 256-270.
- Kilo, R. A., & Hassmén, P. (2016). Burnout and turnover intentions in Australian coaches as related to organizational support and perceived control. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 11(2), 151-161.
- Kim, H. J., Hur, W. M., Moon, T. W., & Jun, J. K. (2017). Is all support equal? The moderating effects of supervisor, coworker, and organizational support on the link between emotional labor and job performance. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 20(2), 124-136.
- Leavy, R. L. (1983). Social support and psychological disorder: A review. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 11(1), 3-21.
- Lee, Y. H., & Chelladurai, P. (2018). Emotional intelligence, emotional labor, coach burnout, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in sport leadership. *European Sport Management Quarterly*, 18(4), 393-412.
- Lim, H., & Lee, S. M. (2025). The reciprocal relationship between emotion regulation and emotional exhaustion among Korean school counselors. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 103(2), 229-241.
- Locke, E. A. (1976). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M. D. Dunnette (Ed.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 1297–1349).
- Maslach, C. A. (1982). *Burnout: The cost of caring*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Maslach, C., & Jackson, S. E. (1981). The measurement of experienced burnout. *Journal of Occupational Behavior*, 2(2), 99–113.

- Maslach, C., and Schaufeli, W.B. (1993). Historical and conceptual development of burnout. In: W.B. Schaufeli, C. Maslach, and T. Marek (Eds.), *Professional burnout: Recent developments in theory and research* (pp. 1-16). Washington, DC: Taylor and Francis.
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61–89.
- Miao, C., Humphrey, R. H., & Qian, S. (2017). A meta-analysis of emotional intelligence and work attitudes. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 90(2), 177-202.
- Mikolajczak, M., Menil, C., & Luminet, O. (2007). Explaining the protective effect of trait emotional intelligence regarding occupational stress: Exploration of emotional labor processes. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 41(5), 1107-1117.
- Mohsin, A., Lengler, J., and Kumar, B. (2013). Exploring the antecedents of intentions to leave the job: the case of luxury hotel staff. *Int. J. Hosp. Manag.* 35, 48–58.
- Moreno-Martínez, M., & Sánchez-Martínez, I. (2025, January). The associated factors of work engagement, work overload, work satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion and their effect on healthcare workers: A cross-sectional study. *Healthcare*, 13(1), Article 96. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare13010096>
- Morris, J. A., & Feldman, D. C. (1996). The dimensions, antecedents, and consequences of emotional labor. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(4), 986-1010.
- Nadiri, H., & Tanova, C. (2010). An investigation of the role of justice in turnover intentions, job satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behavior in the hospitality industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(1), 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2009.05.001>
- Podsakoff, P. M., & Organ, D. W. (1986). Self-reports in organizational research: Problems and prospects. *Journal of Management*, 12(4), 531–544. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920638601200408>
- Peng, X., Ma, J., Chen, Y., Han, Y., Zhou, H., Gong, A., ... & Zeng, Q. (2025). The moderating effect of psychological capital on the relationship between nurses' perceived workplace bullying and emotional exhaustion: a cross-sectional study. *BMC nursing*, 24(1), 103.
- Price, J. L. (2001). Reflections on the determinants of voluntary turnover. *International Journal of Manpower*, 22(7), 600–624. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000006234>
- Rafaeli, A., & Sutton, R. I. (1987). Expression of emotion as part of the work role. *Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), 23–37.
- Rhoades, L., & Eisenberger, R. (2002). Perceived organizational support: a review of the literature. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(4), 698.
- Roscoe, J. T. (1975). *Fundamental research statistics for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.

- Sharma, A., Chawla, V., Guda, S., Rangarajan, D., & Swain, A. K. (2025). Adaptive selling, anxiety, and emotional exhaustion among salespeople. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 33(2), 331-348.
- Strydonck, V. (2025). Linking leaders' learning goal orientation to employees' innovative work behavior, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion: leaders' provision of learning-oriented goals and feedback and coaching accuracy. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 34(1), 109-127.
- Süzer, A. S. (2025). Havacılık Sektörü Çalışanlarında Duygusal Emek Davranışının Çalışanların Tükenmişlik Düzeyine Etkisi. Bir Havayolu Şirketi Örneği. *Üçüncü Sektör Sosyal Ekonomi Dergisi*, 60(1), 764-778.
- Swan, J. E. (1981). Disconfirmation of expectations and satisfaction with a retail service. *Journal of Retailing*, 57(3), 49-67.
- Taris, T. W., Schreurs, P. J. G., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demand-control model and absenteeism: A meta-analysis of empirical findings. *Work & Stress*, 15(2), 125-144.
- Terry, D., Jacobs, S., Moloney, W., East, L., Ryan, L., Elliott, J., ... & Peck, B. (2025). The Impact of Thriving at Work and Occupational Supports: Early Career Nurse Intentions to Leave an Organization and Profession. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 1-12.
- Tett, R. P., & Meyer, J. P. (1993). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, turnover intention, and turnover: path analyses based on meta-analytic findings. *Personnel Psychology*, 46(2), 259-293.
- Van Strydonck, I., Decramer, A., & Audenaert, M. (2025). Linking leaders' learning goal orientation to employees' innovative work behavior, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion: leaders' provision of learning-oriented goals and feedback and coaching accuracy. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 34(1), 109-127.
- Wang, M. L., Lin, C. W., Mayer, N. M., Hu, M. H., & Lee, P. Y. (2016, May). A brain-computer interface for a video content analysis system to perceive emotions by using EEG. In 2016 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics-Taiwan (ICCE-TW) (pp. 1-2). IEEE.
- Wicaksana, D. P., & Wijayanti, A. (2025). The effect of work-family conflict on auditor performance with emotional exhaustion and job satisfaction as mediating variables in auditors who work in public accounting firms (KAP) in Jakarta. *International Journal of Research on Finance & Business*, 4(1), 196-213.
- Wright, T. A., & Hobfoll, S. E. (2004). Commitment, psychological well-being, and job performance: An examination of conservation of resources (COR) theory and job burnout. *Journal of Business and Management*, 9(4), 389-406.